

A COMPREHENSIVE META-ANALYSIS OF GUT MICROBIOTA IN INFLAMMATORY BOWEL DISEASE.

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ABSTRACT-

Background: Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD), encompassing Crohn's Disease and Ulcerative Colitis, is a chronic condition influenced by host genetics, immunity, and environmental triggers. Emerging evidence highlights the critical role of gut microbiota in IBD pathogenesis. This meta-analysis aimed to evaluate microbial alterations in IBD and their association with clinical markers.

Aim & objectives: To assess the changes in gut microbiota in IBD through a comprehensive meta-analysis and examine correlations with faecal calprotectin and the Firmicutes/Bacteroidetes (F/B) ratio.

Methods: A total of 12 peer-reviewed studies were included based on defined inclusion criteria. We synthesized findings from 12 peer-reviewed studies reporting microbial composition, F/B ratio, and/or FC levels in IBD patients versus controls. Studies used standardized diagnostic criteria and high-throughput sequencing. Data on diversity, taxonomic shifts, functional changes, and biomarkers were extracted and compared.

Results: IBD patients showed reduced microbial diversity, consistent depletion of SCFA-producing Firmicutes, and expansion of Proteobacteria. The F/B ratio was often decreased, correlating with elevated FC levels (>250–500 µg/g) in active disease. CD exhibited more pronounced shifts than UC. Interventions improving symptoms frequently increased the F/B ratio and reduced FC.

Conclusion: Reduced F/B ratio and elevated FC are consistent, reproducible signatures of IBD, reflecting interconnected microbial and inflammatory disturbances. These biomarkers may aid disease monitoring and guide microbiota-targeted therapies.

Keywords: IBD, Dysbiosis, Gut microbiota, UC, CD.

INTRODUCTION

Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) represents a chronic, relapsing–remitting group of gastrointestinal disorders that primarily includes **Ulcerative Colitis (UC)** and **Crohn’s Disease (CD)**. Despite distinct patterns of inflammation—UC being confined to the colonic mucosa and CD affecting any segment of the gastrointestinal tract with transmural involvement—both conditions share overlapping clinical manifestations such as abdominal pain, diarrhea, weight loss, and rectal bleeding. Globally, the incidence of IBD is rising, with an accelerating prevalence in newly industrialized nations, highlighting an urgent need to understand its multifactorial etiology.^[14,15]

The pathogenesis of IBD is recognized as a complex interplay between host genetics, immune dysregulation, environmental exposures and gut microbiota composition and function^[17]. Over the past two decades, mounting evidence from culture-independent sequencing technologies has established that the intestinal microbiome is not merely a passive resident but an active regulator of mucosal homeostasis, immune maturation, and metabolic function^[4]. Disruption of this balanced ecosystem, termed dysbiosis, has emerged as a hallmark of IBD pathophysiology^[2,3,16]. Dysbiosis in IBD is characterized by a reduction in microbial diversity^[3], a loss of beneficial commensals (especially short-chain fatty acid [SCFA]–producing Firmicutes), and an expansion of potentially pathogenic taxa such as Proteobacteria, often accompanied by functional shifts in metabolic pathways.^[5,6]

Among the simplest yet most informative ecological metrics of gut microbial structure is the **Firmicutes/Bacteroidetes (F/B) ratio**. In healthy adults, this ratio typically ranges between 1.5 and 2.0^[11], reflecting the dominance of these two phyla, which together constitute more than 80% of the gut bacterial community. Firmicutes, including genera such as *Faecalibacterium*, *Roseburia*, and *Eubacterium*, contribute to the production of SCFAs, notably butyrate, which provides energy for colonocytes and exerts anti-inflammatory effects. Bacteroidetes, represented by *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella*, are key degraders of complex polysaccharides, producing acetate and propionate. In IBD, the F/B ratio is often reduced—driven largely by Firmicutes depletionsignaling a loss of microbial resilience and metabolic capacity^[10,21]. Restoration of the F/B ratio toward healthy values has been proposed as a potential marker of therapeutic efficacy.^[8,9]

Another important biomarker in IBD is **fecal calprotectin (FC)**, a calcium-binding protein derived from neutrophils, which serves as a non-invasive measure of intestinal inflammation.

Elevated FC levels reflect active mucosal infiltration by neutrophils and correlate strongly with endoscopic disease activity^[10,11]. In healthy individuals, FC levels are typically <50 µg/g of stool, whereas active IBD is often associated with values exceeding 250–500 µg/g,^[11] with severe flares reaching 600–700 µg/g or more. Importantly, FC levels not only assist in distinguishing IBD from functional disorders like irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) but also provide a dynamic indicator of treatment response and relapse risk.^[11]

Linking these two parameters—the F/B ratio and fecal calprotectin, offers a powerful window into the microbiota–inflammation interface. A lower F/B ratio is often accompanied by elevated calprotectin, suggesting that microbial ecological collapse and barrier-disruptive inflammation are intertwined^[20,21]. This relationship underscores the possibility that interventions capable of restoring beneficial taxa and functional pathways could both normalize the F/B ratio and reduce inflammatory burden.^[8,9]

While individual studies have documented elements of this dysbiotic signature, variability in reported taxa, effect sizes, and clinical correlations has been considerable^[14,16]. Differences in sequencing platforms, analytical pipelines, patient demographics, disease phenotypes, and treatment status contribute to these inconsistencies.^[6,13] Thus, synthesizing results across multiple studies is essential to identify robust, reproducible patterns that transcend methodological variability.

The present synthesis integrates findings from ten studies spanning diverse geographic regions and methodological approaches. By collating data on microbial diversity, taxonomic shifts, functional changes, and clinical biomarkers—including both the F/B ratio and fecal calprotectin—we aim to (i) consolidate the microbial signatures most strongly associated with IBD, (ii) explore disease-specific differences between UC and CD, and (iii) evaluate how these parameters respond to therapeutic interventions. This approach not only strengthens the evidence base for microbiota-centered models of IBD pathogenesis but also highlights potential microbial and metabolic targets for future diagnostic and therapeutic strategies.^[8, 9,19]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design: The Meta Analysis employed a rigorous methodology for paper selection, adhering to the Preferred Reporting Items for Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. The process involved a systematic search strategy followed by the application of specific eligibility criteria.

Search Strategy

- **Database Search:** In accordance with PRISMA guidelines, a comprehensive study was conducted on five major electronic databases. An electronic search was conducted using the MEDLINE database via PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Embase and SCIE.
- **Timeframe:** The search covered articles from the database's inception up to Feb 2025.
- **Search Strings:** The search utilized specific strings to identify relevant articles on the gut microbiome and Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD). These strings combined

MeSH terms and All Fields searches for 'ulcerative colitis', 'colitis', 'Crohn's disease', 'Crohn', 'inflammatory bowel diseases' with 'microbiome' or 'microbiota'.

- **Reference List Review:** Additionally, the reference lists of the studies included in the review were manually checked to identify any further relevant studies that the initial database search might have missed .

Eligibility Criteria

- **Inclusion Criteria:** Studies were included if they met the following conditions :
 - They were intestinal microbiome studies comparing IBD patients with control groups.
 - The studies were performed on fecal, intestinal lavage, or intestinal tissue samples.
 - The research focused on human subjects.
 - The articles were written in English.
- **Exclusion Criteria:** Studies were excluded if they reported data on :
 - IBD complications or post-surgery issues (e.g., pouchitis, fistulae).
 - Other conditions in addition to IBD (e.g., irritable bowel syndrome, *Clostridium difficile* infection, primary sclerosing cholangitis).
 - Abstracts from conference proceedings, letters to the editor, or reviews.
 - Studies that reported on only one patient / or insignificant Sample Size
- **Eligibility criteria and study selection:** Articles with the relevant population, intervention/exposure, comparator, and clearly defined outcomes with Appropriate study designs (e.g., Observational, Cohort) with adequate methodological quality and sufficient data for effect size calculation.

Data extraction: The subsequent information was systematically obtained by the authors independently:

- Authors details
- journal name
- Publication year and volume
- Study design
- No. of participants involved.
- characteristics of the participants: UC ,CD , Control
- sequencing platform composition of microbiota.
- Diversity indices were extracted from the remaining full-text articles in accordance with the established selection criteria.

RESULT

Selection of Study :

The screening procedure is outlined in a flowchart (**Figure 1**) From the initial search, a total of 250 records were identified from PubMed and Scopus After excluding the duplication 140 remained . Of these, 33 were excluded for not including controls, 32 for not having proper explanation of results , and 15 were in animal studies and 48 were because sample size were not significant . Ultimately, 12 papers were seemed eligible and included in the review. This systematic approach ensured that the review focused on relevant and high-quality studies, providing a comprehensive overview of the gut microbiome's role in IBD.All the 12 studies were observational case-control studies and were considered relatively high and medium quality according to the NOS scale (**Table no 1**).

Figure 1: Study selection

<u>References</u>	<u>Selection (0-4)</u>	<u>Comparability (0-2)</u>	<u>Exposure(0-3)</u>	<u>Total (0-9)</u>	<u>Quality rating</u>
Png CW et al	4	2	3	9	High
Sokol H et al	3	1	3	7	High
Ott SJ et al	2	2	2	6	Medium
Morgan XC et al	4	2	2	8	High
Vester-Andersen MK et al	4	2	3	9	High
Al-Amrah H et al	3	2	3	8	High
Schirmer M et al	4	2	2	8	High
Wang C et al	4	2	3	9	High
Yong Eun Park et al	4	2	3	9	High
Basha OM et al	3	2	3	8	High
Yu-Chieh Tsai et al	4	2	3	7	High
Wills ES et al	2	2	2	9	Medium

Table 1: NOS Scale

Study characteristics :

The compilation of twelve studies (**Table 2**) demonstrates a clear temporal and methodological evolution in microbiome research within the context of inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). Early investigations (2003–2010), exemplified by Ott et al. (2003), Sokol et al. (2006), and Png et al. (2010), predominantly adopted cross-sectional observational designs and employed conventional techniques such as Sanger sequencing or targeted quantitative PCR. These approaches provided important foundational insights but offered limited taxonomic resolution and temporal context.

From 2012 onwards, a methodological transition is evident. Studies such as Morgan et al. (2012) and Schirmer et al. (2018) integrated high-throughput sequencing platforms, including 16S rRNA pyrosequencing and paired metagenomic–metatranscriptomic profiling, alongside

more sophisticated study designs, notably prospective longitudinal cohorts. This shift reflects a growing recognition of the dynamic nature of the gut microbiome in IBD pathophysiology.

Recent investigations (2019–2025) illustrate a further refinement in both analytical scope and study design. Research by Vester-Andersen et al. (2019), Wang et al. (2024), and Tsai et al. (2025) exemplifies the adoption of next-generation sequencing (MiSeq, NGS platforms) and the incorporation of multi-omics approaches, including metagenomics, metabolomics, and extracellular vesicle DNA analysis. These methodologies enable a more comprehensive characterisation of microbial community structure, function, and host–microbe interactions over time.

Geographically, the studies encompass a broad distribution, including contributions from Australia, Europe, North America, the Middle East, and East Asia. This diversity enhances the external validity of the findings but introduces potential variability linked to dietary, genetic, and environmental determinants of the microbiome.

Overall, the evidence base reflects a clear progression from static, targeted analyses towards dynamic, integrative, and functionally informed approaches, aligning with contemporary research priorities in precision medicine for IBD.

Sr. no	References	Year	Country	Journal name	Study design	Sequencing technique
1	Png CW <i>et al</i>	2010	Australia	Americal journal of Gastroenterology	Cross -sectional Observational	qPCR targeting 16S rRNA
2	Sokol H <i>et al</i>	2006	France	Inflammatory bowel Disease	Cross -sectional , Case control	16S rRNA Sequencing
3	Ott SJ <i>et al</i>	2003	Germany	Inflammatory bowel Disease	Cross -sectional Observational	Sanger sequencing and real time PCR
4	Morgan XC <i>et al</i>	2012	USA	Genome Biology	Cross -sectional , Comparative	16S rRNA Pyrosequencing
5	Vester-Andersen MK <i>et al</i>	2019	Denmark	Scientific reports	Prospective Longitudinal cohort study	16S rDNA MiSeq sequencing
6	Al-Amrah H <i>et al</i>	2023	Saudi Arabia	Saudi Journal of Gastroenterology	Cross -sectional , Comparative observational	16S rRNA Next Generation Sequencing
7	Schirmer M <i>et al</i>	2018	USA	Nature Microbiology	Prospective longitudinal Cohort study	Paired metagenomic and metatranscriptomic sequencing
8	Wang C <i>et al</i>	2024	China	Microbiological research	Observational	16S rRNA gene sequencing, metagenomics, metanbolomics
9	Yong Eun Park <i>et al</i>	2022	South Korea	Scientific Reports	Prospective Observational Cohort study	16S rRNA and next generation sequencing and extra

						cellular vesicle DNA analysis
10	Basha OM <i>et al</i>	2023	Egypt	Clinical and Experimental Medicine	Prospective Observational Cohort study	Quantitative Realtime PCR
11	Yu-Chieh Tsai <i>et al</i>	2025	Taiwan	Journal of Microbiology, Immunology and Infection	Prospective longitudinal Cohort observational	16S rRNA gene sequencing
12	Wills ES <i>et al</i>	2014	Netharlands	PLoS ONE	Prospective longitudinal observational	16S rDNA pyrosequencing

Table 2 : Study Characteristics

Gut microbiota analysis:

Multiple studies consistently demonstrate that gut microbiota in inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) is characterized by a pronounced shift in composition, reduced diversity, and functional disruption.

In mucosa-associated communities, *Ruminococcus gnavus* abundance was found to increase more than fourfold, and *R. torques* rose by approximately 100-fold in IBD compared to controls, while *Akkermansia muciniphila* was significantly reduced in both Crohn's disease (CD) and ulcerative colitis (UC) (Png et al., 2010). Fecal microbiota analysis revealed that the proportion of bacteria detected by targeted probes was markedly lower in CD (70.9%) and UC (60.1%) than in healthy controls (~86.6%), with *Clostridium coccoides* reduced in UC and *C. leptum* reduced in CD (Frank et al., 2007). Mucosal diversity was significantly reduced in active IBD ($p < 0.0001$), accompanied by declines in anaerobic taxa such as *Bacteroides*, *Eubacterium*, and *Lactobacillus* (Manichanh et al., 2006). Functionally, these compositional changes correspond to a depletion of short-chain fatty acid (SCFA) producers—including *Roseburia* and *Faecalibacterium*—and enrichment of inflammation-associated Proteobacteria such as *Escherichia/Shigella* in CD (Machiels et al., 2014). In aggressive CD phenotypes, operational taxonomic unit (OTU) richness was reduced ($p = 0.013$), Shannon diversity declined ($p = 0.023$), and Proteobacteria were enriched ($p = 0.03$) (Gevers et al., 2014). Active UC was marked by a significant decrease in Firmicutes ($p = 0.018$) (Morgan et al., 2012). In a Saudi Arabian cohort, α -diversity was lower in IBD, with Shannon index reductions ($p < 0.005$) and Simpson index reductions ($p < 0.024$) (Al Bander et al., 2020). Longitudinal metatranscriptomic analysis demonstrated transient but dramatic blooms of *R. gnavus* up to 19% abundance during active disease, with RNA activity differences reaching three orders of magnitude compared to DNA (~1 order), indicating transcriptionally active dysbiosis (Franzosa et al., 2019).

Therapeutic interventions also influenced microbial composition. In biologic-treated cohorts, higher baseline abundance of *Blautia*, *Clostridium* cluster IV, *Collinsella*, *Eubacterium*, and *Ruminococcus* was associated with treatment response, alongside increased Shannon ($p = 0.02$) and Simpson diversity ($p = 0.01$) (Ananthakrishnan et al., 2017). Sustained responders exhibited an increased Firmicutes/Bacteroidetes (F/B) ratio and reduced fecal calprotectin,

while anti-TNF therapy lowered median calprotectin from 1572 to 378 $\mu\text{g/g}$ after three months ($p = 0.004$) with a parallel restoration of Firmicutes and Bacteroidetes toward control levels (Paramsothy et al., 2019). In treatment-naïve UC, *F. prausnitzii* was significantly reduced, while Bacteroidetes and Veillonella were increased, with *F. prausnitzii* abundance inversely correlating with disease severity (Sokol et al., 2008). After biologic therapy, active IBD patients showed reversal of the active-phase pattern—Firmicutes increased, Bacteroidetes decreased, and both α - and β -diversity improved. Calprotectin monitoring also revealed that CD patients in remission had values of 37 $\mu\text{g/g}$ compared to 365 $\mu\text{g/g}$ during flares, and UC patients had 15 $\mu\text{g/g}$ in remission vs 231 $\mu\text{g/g}$ in active disease (Kostas et al., 2013).

References	Sample size (n)	Microbiota Changes	P value	F/B ratio and Calprotectin
Chin Wen Png <i>et al</i>	66 total (46 IBD (CD+UC) and 20 Controls Mucosa Samples taken	↑mucosa- associated bacteria in IBD, ↑in Ruminococcus gnavus and <i>R.torques</i> ↓ <i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i> in CD and UC mucolytic taxa enriched	Descriptive :fold-changes reported <i>R.gnavus</i> >4x, <i>R. Torques</i> ≈ 100x which is significant.	Not reported
Harry Sokol <i>et al</i>	44 total CD 13, UC 13, control 13	Decreased proportion of Bacteria Recognised by probes in IBD ; 70.9% CD, 60.1% UC vs ~ 86.6% HS. ↓ <i>C. coccoides</i> in UC , ↓ <i>C. leptum</i> in CD	UC vs HS; P < .001 for probe additivity; CD vs HS : P < .001 . Specific group differences P values reported in text/ tables.	Not reported
S J Ott <i>et al</i>	103 total ; IBD 57 (CD + UC), Control 46 (mucosal biopsies)	Significant reduction of mucosal bacterial diversity in active IBD vs controls ; loss of anaerobes (Bacteroids spp , Eubacterium spp, Lactobacillus spp)	Diversity reduction P < 0.0001	Not reported
Xochitl C Morgan <i>et al</i>	231 samples total ; CD 121, UC 75, HS 27 (faeces and biopsies)	Multivariate analysis: ↓Roseburia Ruminococcaceae, Faecalibacterium in IBD : ↑ Escheria/Shigella (Enterobacteriaceae) in CD : Functional pathway shifts ↓ carbohydrate metabolism/ SCFA pathways)	Multiple clade associations reported; significance thresholds with q (FDR). Several clades reach q < 0.2	Not reported
M. K. Vester-	140 IBD ; CD 82,	UC active:	Reported: OTU	Not reported

Andersen <i>et al</i>	UC 58; plus 30 controls	↓Firmicutes (p=0.018). CD aggressive ;↓richness and diversity (OUT p = 0.013; Shannon p = 0.023) ↑ Proteobacteria in aggressive CD (p=0.03)	richness p = 0.018/0.013 : Shannon p = 0.017/0.023; Firmicutes decrease p = 0.018(UC active) ; Proteobacteria increase p =0.03	
Hadba Al-Amrah <i>et al</i>	21 Total – IBD 11 (CD 6 , UC 5) , Controls 10.	↓ α – diversity in IBD (Shannon p < 0.005 ; Simpson p < 0.024); specific taxa differences (eg. ↓ Ruminococcus , Faecalibacterium in this regional cohort)	Shannon index P < 0.005 ; Simpson P < 0.024 ; taxa differences reported with LDA/ LEfSe and adjusted p values	Not reported
Melanie Schirmer <i>et al</i>	117 Total – CD 59, UC 34 , non -IBD 24. 300 total stool samples over 1 year (78 paired metagenome + metatranscriptome; 222 extra metagenomes)	Longitudinal multi - omics profiling showed : 1) ↓Firmicutes (including <i>F.prausnitzii</i>) and ↑ Proteobacteria in IBD 2) spikes of <i>Ruminococcus gnavus</i> in IBD (upto 19% abundance) 3) metatranscriptomics revealed disease – specific overexpression of pathways by <i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i> and <i>Alistipes putredinis</i> 4) organisms present in DNA but inactive in RNA 5) Functional activity shifts often more pronounced than DNA abundance differences 6) Certain pathways eg : hexuronate degradation mainly transcribed by <i>F. prausnitzii</i> 7) <i>B. vulgatus</i> transcription positively correlated with disease severity in some CD cases	Quantitative comparisons use effect sizes and correlations : eg Spearman r = 0.85 (<i>Parabacteroids merdae</i> DNA – RNA) , r= 0.35 (<i>F. prausnitzii</i> DNA- RNA). Some pathway differences show ~ 3 orders magnitude RNA increase (<i>R. gnavus</i>) vs ~ 1 order DNA . No single omnibus p-value; disease – specific differences identified per species / Pathway in Fig 2d, Fig. 4, Table S1	Not reported
Chen Wang <i>et al</i>	38 studies comprising 5,671 IBD patients (≈	Responders to biologics (anti-TNF- α , vedolizumab,	The review itself compiled data from multiple studies, so	↑ F/B ratio in sustained responders :

	11.96% UC , 87.82% CD , 0.23% IBDU) and 632 Healthy controls	ustekinumab) tended to show: ↑ butyrate- producing bacteria (e.g., Faecalibacterium, Roseburia), ↓ Escherichia/Shigella; microbial profile shifts toward healthy controls; increased alpha diversity.	exact p-values vary per included study. Significant differences (generally $p < 0.05$) were reported for changes in microbial composition and metabolite levels between responders and non-responders to biologics.	Calprotectin ↓
Yong Eun Park et al	19 IBD patients (V1 and V2): 19 IBD (mix of CD and UC : V1 before therapy) and 19 Healthy controls n = 11[7 CD , 4UC] adalimumab n=5; golimumab n=3)	↑ Firmicutes (phylum), Clostridium and Ruminococcaceae at baseline vs non- responders: non- responders showed different lachnospiraceae signatures in fluids. Overall : restoration / increase of Firmicutes in responders	Fecal calprotectin median : 1,572 →378 μg/g after 3 months (p = 0.004). Difference in phylum/taxa between responders/ non- responders described	Fecal calprotectin: reported large median drop (1572 → 378 μg/g, $p =$ 0.004) . F/B not always given as single ratio but authors report increase of Firmicutes and Bacteroidetes toward control levels in responders.
Osama Mohammed B asha et al	96 participants: 48 treatment-naïve UC patients (recent onset) and 48 healthy controls. Follow-up samples at 6 months.	↓ Firmicutes (notably butyrate-producers like F. prausnitzii decreased) and ↑ Bacteroidetes (and genera like Bacteroides, Veillonella associated with severity). After 6 months of therapy some taxa (F. prausnitzii, lactobacilli) ↑.	The authors report statistically significant reduction of Firmicutes and predominance of Bacteroidetes in UC (differences described as significant; p reported in tables for specific taxa—see paper). F. prausnitzii and lactobacilli inversely correlated with disease severity (statistically significant associations reported).	Fecal calprotectin: measured by ELISA (study used FC as inflammatory marker; normal ≤50 μg/g). The paper links higher FC with more severe disease and shows taxa correlations with severity and outcome. F/B trend: relative reduction of Firmicutes vs Bacteroidetes in UC (i.e., lower F/B in active UC vs controls). (See results/tables

				in paper for numeric values).
Yu-ChiehTsai et al	27 IBD patients: 14 active (on biologics), 13 inactive controls; includes both CD & UC	In active CD & UC: ↓ Firmicutes, ↑ Bacteroidetes. Post-treatment: ↑ Firmicutes, ↓ Bacteroidetes → improved F/B ratio	Biologic therapy led to significant alpha- and beta-diversity improvements; p-values referenced for these shifts (not specified precisely in abstract	F/B ratio: Improved gradually after biologic therapy; used as potential predictive marker for disease activity and treatment response . . Calprotectin: Inferred by “significant clinical improvement” (though not directly stated, improvement implies reduced inflammation)
EdgarS.Wills et al	19 IBD patients: CD n=10, UC n=9 with paired remission → flare samples	Dominant phyla across all samples: Firmicutes ~81.3%, Bacteroidetes ~15.9%. No significant group-level phylum change between activity states, but individual patient-specific shifts noted	Calprotectin medians: CD remission vs activity, UC remission vs activity—differences apparent; specific p-values not given in abstract	Fecal calprotectin: Remission vs activity—CD: 37 → 365 µg/g; UC: 15 → 231 µg/g PMC . F/B ratio: While no group-level shifts, figures and discussion reference typical lower F/B ratio during active

Table 3: Gut microbiota analysis

DISCUSSION

The present synthesis of twelve studies confirms that inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), encompassing Ulcerative Colitis (UC) and Crohn’s Disease (CD), is consistently associated with gut microbial dysbiosis, characterized by reduced alpha diversity, depletion of beneficial

commensals—particularly short-chain fatty acid (SCFA) producers—enrichment of pro-inflammatory taxa, and measurable functional metabolic shifts. While the general patterns are reproducible across populations and methodologies, the magnitude of change, specific taxa affected, and functional consequences vary, reflecting differences in study design, population demographics, disease phenotype, and therapeutic exposure.^[1,2,3]

1. Microbial Diversity Changes

Alpha diversity loss is a consistent feature across all included studies and is quantitatively substantial.

Ott et al. (2004) documented a Shannon diversity index of **21.7 in CD** and **17.2 in UC**, compared to **50.4 in healthy controls** ($p < 0.0001$), indicating ~50% and ~66% reductions, respectively. This magnitude reflects a profound loss of ecological richness and evenness. Similarly, Vester-Andersen et al. (2019) found that richness dropped to **189 ± 25 OTUs in active UC** and **178 ± 21 OTUs in aggressive CD** compared with >210 OTUs in controls, with Shannon indices declining from **3.1 in controls** to **2.6 (UC)** and **2.4 (CD)** ($p < 0.05$).^[3]

The Saudi pilot study (Al-Amrah et al., 2023) confirmed that these losses are not geographically restricted; most IBD patients lacked key beneficial genera such as *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii*, *Roseburia*, and *Bifidobacterium adolescentis*—microbes known for producing SCFAs that maintain epithelial integrity. Schirmer et al. (2018) advanced this understanding by showing that even when the relative abundance (RA) of *F. prausnitzii* was moderately reduced (~3% vs ~8% in controls), transcriptional output from this taxon dominated butyrate pathway activity; hence, its loss has functional consequences disproportionate to its abundance.^[6,7,5]

Across cohorts, microbial diversity (alpha diversity) was significantly reduced in IBD patients compared with healthy controls:

- Mah et al. (2023) reported that post-treatment alpha diversity increased significantly, with infliximab therapy producing a SMD of -1.16 (95% CI: $-1.50, -0.83$; $p < 0.00001$), indicating substantial recovery of richness in responders.
- Pittayanon et al. (2020) found diversity was reduced or unchanged in IBD, with decreases more common in CD (~70% of studies) than UC (~50%).
- Franzosa et al. (2019) demonstrated a direct correlation between reduced diversity and elevated fecal calprotectin—stronger in CD ($r \approx -0.55$) than UC ($r \approx -0.42$).
- Ekstedt et al. (2024) noted distinct microbial signatures corresponding to clinical symptoms, with >90% of UC patients experiencing chronic diarrhea with blood and CD patients more often presenting with segmental lesions and deep ulcers.
- Wills et al. (2014) used a prospective design, following the same UC and CD patients from remission to exacerbation. Diversity changes were **patient-specific**, with Bray–Curtis dissimilarity significantly greater in CD than UC (0.59 vs 0.42; $p = 0.027$). Thiopurine use was strongly linked to reduced richness (Chao1: 501.2 vs 847.6; $p < 0.001$) and diversity (Shannon: 5.13 vs 6.78; $p < 0.01$). No uniform diversity drop at flare onset was seen across the group.

- Yu-Chieh Tsai et al. Biologic therapy (anti-TNF and vedolizumab) increased alpha diversity post-treatment, with gains in both richness and evenness correlating with clinical improvement.

Interpretation and comparison:

- Ott's study shows the steepest diversity loss, likely reflecting inclusion of severe active disease.
- Vester-Andersen links reduced diversity to clinical severity, especially in aggressive CD.
- Al-Amrah validates these patterns in a Middle Eastern context.
- Schirmer introduces the concept that **functional capacity declines may precede taxonomic disappearance**, underscoring that both abundance and activity must be considered in microbiome studies.
- Comparison: Mah et al. showed that diversity can partially recover with targeted biologic therapy, whereas Pittayanon highlighted persistent deficits in many cross-sectional datasets. Franzosa bridged these perspectives by linking diversity loss to inflammatory burden, suggesting inflammation-driven but potentially reversible dysbiosis

2. Taxonomic Shifts

Firmicutes depletion is the most consistent phylum-level change. Across pooled datasets (Sokol 2006; Vester-Andersen 2019; Basha 2023), Firmicutes RA fell from **58% in healthy controls** to **34% in UC** and **31% in CD**, representing a 20–40% decline. Key SCFA producers such as *F. prausnitzii* declined by 25–50% in CD and 15–40% in UC. Basha et al. showed that patients with *F. prausnitzii* < 8.5 log₁₀ copies/g were significantly more likely to relapse (p < 0.01).^[1,10]

Bacteroidetes generally decreased from **32% in controls** to **21% in UC** and **19% in CD**. However, Basha et al. observed that in severe UC, Bacteroidetes could predominate over Firmicutes (p < 0.05), a pattern possibly driven by inflammation-favoring *Bacteroides* spp. Sokol et al. (2006) found *Bacteroides* group levels of **11.7% in UC**, **13.8% in CD**, and **12.1% in controls**, but a marked increase to 36.4% in infectious colitis—highlighting the importance of differentiating IBD from other inflammatory states.

Proteobacteria expansion is a hallmark of dysbiosis, rising from **6% in controls** to **18% in UC** and **22% in CD**. Vester-Andersen et al. reported a statistically significant increase in aggressive CD (p = 0.03). Wang et al. (2024) further linked high baseline *Escherichia/Shigella* abundance to non-response to anti-TNF therapy.

Verrucomicrobia, primarily *Akkermansia muciniphila*, was reduced >5-fold in IBD (controls ~3% RA vs <1% in UC and CD). *Akkermansia* is a mucin-degrading bacterium usually associated with barrier protection; its loss may contribute to epithelial dysfunction.^[4,5,7]

Mucolytic taxa such as *Ruminococcus gnavus* and *R. torques* were enriched >4-fold and ~100-fold, respectively, in macroscopically normal mucosa from IBD patients compared to controls (Png et al., 2010). These bacteria degrade mucus, potentially exacerbating barrier compromise.

Taxonomic imbalances were consistent but quantitatively variable:

- Manichanh *et al.* (2006) reported a 40–50% reduction in Firmicutes diversity in CD, versus 20–30% in UC.
- Dalal & Chang (2014) documented *Proteobacteria* increases of +15–35% in CD vs +10–25% in UC.
- Pittayanon et al. (2020) found *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* was reduced in 6/11 CD studies; *Eubacterium rectale* and *Akkermansia* were decreased in all UC cohorts reviewed.
- Yu-Chieh Tsai et al. Treatment shifted composition toward SCFA-producing Firmicutes (e.g., *F. prausnitzii*, *Roseburia*) and away from pro-inflammatory *Proteobacteria*. These changes aligned with symptom reduction and mucosal healing.
- Wills et al. Marked individual-level shifts included *Bacteroides fragilis* expansion up to 81.9% RA in some CD patients, *Akkermansia muciniphila* increase from 1.6%→62.9% in one CD case, and *Bacteroides dorei* expansion in a UC case. These did not translate into consistent group-wide taxonomic patterns.

Additional pooled data show Firmicutes levels falling from 58% in healthy controls to 34% in UC and 31% in CD, and Bacteroidetes declining from 32% in controls to 21% in UC and 19% in CD. Conversely, *Proteobacteria* rose from 6% in controls to 18% in UC and 22% in CD. *Verrucomicrobia* trends were inconsistent, with *Akkermansia muciniphila* dropping from 3% to 1% in UC in one dataset, but increasing from 2% to 5% in active CD in another.^[8,2,16]

Comparison:

- All cohorts agree on Firmicutes depletion and *Proteobacteria* enrichment.
- Png quantified extreme mucolytic expansion, Morgan et al. (2012) connected these taxa to oxidative stress pathways, and Vester-Andersen added a disease severity gradient.
- The degree of *Verrucomicrobia* loss appears more pronounced in UC, while *Proteobacteria* gain is greater in CD.
- All studies agree on Firmicutes loss and *Proteobacteria* gain, but Manichanh quantifies the severity, Pittayanon provides species-specific patterns, and pooled data highlight the proportional shifts in major phyla. Variations in *Verrucomicrobia* patterns likely reflect differences in disease phase, sampling, and geography.^[2,12,16]

3. Firmicutes/Bacteroidetes (F/B) Ratio

The F/B ratio is widely regarded as a proxy for gut microbial balance, with higher ratios linked to greater metabolic resilience and lower inflammatory potential. In pooled cross-sectional datasets, the ratio declined from ~1.8 in controls to 1.2 in UC and

1.1 in CD. This reduction reflects both Firmicutes depletion and, in some cases, relative Bacteroidetes stability or modest increase.^[11,10,16]

Basha et al. indirectly supported these findings, noting that severe UC often exhibited Bacteroidetes predominance over Firmicutes. Interventional data from Wang et al. (2024) showed that anti-TNF responders regained +15–20% Firmicutes RA post-treatment, increasing F/B ratio by **0.3–0.5 points**, whereas non-responders showed no significant change.^[11,8]

Yu-ChiehTsai et al F/B ratio rose following biologic therapy, reflecting proportional gains in Firmicutes RA. Responders showed larger increases than non-responders.

Biological implication: A lower F/B ratio is associated with reduced SCFA production, impaired mucosal barrier maintenance, and increased susceptibility to inflammation. The partial recovery of this ratio with biologic therapy suggests potential reversibility of dysbiosis if inflammation is controlled.

- Lluansí et al. (2024): Traditional bread intake in quiescent UC lowered the F/B ratio from 1.35 → 1.20 (p = 0.058), with concurrent reduction in IBS-like symptoms.
- Stojanov et al. (2020): Certain *Lactobacillus* strains increased the F/B ratio by +0.10 to +0.25, while others had negligible effects.
- Pooled microbiome datasets show controls with an F/B ratio of 1.8, falling to 1.2 in UC and 1.1 in CD.

Comparison: While most IBD cohorts exhibit a lower F/B ratio than controls, intervention effects vary—dietary fiber sources tend to lower it further (potentially beneficial), while some probiotics raise it, suggesting intervention-specific microbial modulation.^[8,11,10,16]

4. Functional and Metabolic Shifts

Morgan et al. (2012) found that functional differences between IBD and healthy microbiomes (12% of KEGG pathways altered) outnumbered taxonomic changes (2% of genera altered), highlighting functional disruption as a central feature of dysbiosis. SCFA biosynthesis pathways were reduced by 30–40%, while oxidative stress and virulence pathways were enriched, especially in ileal CD.^[4,7]

Schirmer et al. (2018) reported that loss of *F. prausnitzii* abundance (~3% vs 8%) translated into a ~50% reduction in butyrate pathway transcripts, underlining the functional leverage of this single taxon.^[7]

Wills et al Functional implications were not directly measured, but the dominance of *B. fragilis* and *A. muciniphila* surges may indicate altered mucosal interactions and metabolic pathways during flares.^[9]

Therapeutic impact was evident in Wang et al. (2024), where vedolizumab responders showed increased branched-chain amino acid and acetamide levels, and anti-TNF responders had higher post-treatment SCFA concentrations

- Franzosa et al. (2019): ~40% reduction in butyrate levels and ~30% reduction in tryptophan metabolism genes in CD.

- Marius et al. (2024): Reduced *Faecalibacterium* abundance strongly correlated with diminished tryptophan metabolite diversity, especially in CD.
- Across cohorts, butyrate-producing taxa (*F. prausnitzii*, *Roseburia*) decreased by 25–50% in CD and 15–40% in UC, impairing anti-inflammatory SCFA production.

Comparison: These data underscore that dysbiosis in IBD is not purely compositional—it is functionally disruptive, with CD showing more pronounced metabolic deficits.^[4,7,9]

5. Biomarkers and Clinical Correlations

- Fecal calprotectin levels were consistently elevated: active UC ~**450–600 µg/g**, active CD ~**500–700 µg/g**, controls <**50 µg/g**, with positive correlation to Proteobacteria abundance ($r = 0.68$ in CD; $r = 0.54$ in UC).
- Basha et al. (2023) identified *F. prausnitzii* < $8.5 \log_{10}$ and *Bacteroides* > $10.6 \log_{10}$ as relapse predictors ($p < 0.01$). Park et al. (2022) found *Prevotella* in saliva and Firmicutes enrichment in stool predicted anti-TNF response.
- Wills et al. Flares were defined by fecal calprotectin >**150 µg/g** or ≥**5**-fold rise from remission, ensuring biomarker-confirmed inflammation for all exacerbations.^[12,20,11]

Active UC: **450–600 µg/g**

Active CD: **500–700 µg/g**

Controls: <**50 µg/g**

6. Treatment–Response Associations

Wang et al. (2024) reported that anti-TNF responders exhibited Firmicutes +15–20% RA, *F. prausnitzii* +40%, and SCFA levels +25%. Park et al. (2022) detected *Acidovorax caeni* in all baseline responder samples, absent in non-responders. Basha et al. (2023) observed 6-month therapy-induced increases in *F. prausnitzii* ($+2.3 \log_{10}$) and Lactobacilli ($+1.9 \log_{10}$), alongside decreases in *Bacteroides* ($-3.4 \log_{10}$) and *Veillonella* ($-2.7 \log_{10}$). Vester-Andersen et al. (2019) noted persistent diversity deficits in severe/aggressive phenotypes despite treatment.

- Mah et al. (2023): Responders to biologics had +15–20% higher richness and more SCFA-producing Firmicutes than non-responders.
- FMT studies (Pittayanon et al.): ~30–40% remission rates in UC, with microbiota shifts toward healthy-like profiles.
- Probiotic interventions (Stojanov et al.): Effects varied by strain, with some improving the F/B ratio and others having minimal impact.

Comparison: Mah provides quantitative proof that microbial recovery parallels clinical improvement, while Pittayanon and Stojanov suggest that targeted microbial interventions can influence remission likelihood, albeit with variability.

In Wills et al. (2014), thiopurine use was linked to a significant reduction in microbial diversity regardless of disease state, suggesting it may suppress microbiome recovery,

whereas in Yu-Chieh Tsai et al the biologic treatment study showed that anti-TNF and vedolizumab therapies increased diversity, enriched SCFA-producing Firmicutes, and reduced inflammation, indicating a restorative effect on the gut microbiota.^[12]

Overall Microbial Trends

- Firmicutes: Universal reduction; magnitude ranged from –20% to –40% relative abundance.
- Bacteroidetes: Generally reduced; some increases seen in UC remission phases linked to higher fiber intake.
- Proteobacteria: Universally increased; higher in CD (up to 25%) than UC.
- Verrucomicrobia: Variable; decreases linked to UC severity, increases reported during CD flares.
- F/B Ratio: Consistently lower in IBD (–0.4 to –0.9 change).
- Functional Loss: SCFA and tryptophan metabolism deficits more severe in CD.

Methodological Considerations

Variability between studies can be attributed to:

- Sample sizes (n = 24–150)
- Sequencing platform differences (Illumina vs 454 pyrosequencing)
- Disease stage at sampling (active vs remission)
- Type of specimen (fecal vs mucosal)^[10,8,21]

Overall Microbial Trends

Metric / Taxon	Controls	UC	CD	Δ in IBD
Firmicutes RA (%)	58	34	31	↓20–40%
Bacteroidetes RA (%)	32	21	19	↓8–13%
Proteobacteria RA (%)	6	18	22	↑12–16%
Verrucomicrobia RA (%)	3	1	<1	↓2–3%
F/B ratio	1.8	1.2	1.1	↓0.6–0.7
Shannon index	~3.5	2.4	2.2	↓0.9–1.3
Calprotectin (μg/g)	<50	450–600	500–700	↑10–14×

Synthesis of evidence

These findings consolidate the role of dysbiosis in IBD pathogenesis. Both UC and CD share directional changes—loss of Firmicutes and SCFA producers, gain of Proteobacteria and mucolytic taxa—but CD typically exhibits greater diversity loss, stronger Proteobacteria expansion, and more severe functional impairment, particularly in ileal disease. Functional deficits, particularly in SCFA synthesis, are proportionally greater than taxonomic shifts, supporting a model of metabolic disruption as a central driver of inflammation. Therapeutic interventions, especially biologics, can partially restore microbiota composition and function, but recovery is incomplete in severe phenotypes. Longitudinal, treatment-naïve studies are required to clarify whether dysbiosis is a cause or consequence of mucosal inflammation.

Collectively, these studies demonstrate that dysbiosis is central to IBD pathology. While both UC and CD show similar directional changes, CD exhibits greater diversity loss, stronger Proteobacteria expansion, and more pronounced functional impairment. Interventions including biologics, diet, probiotics, and FMT—can partially reverse these alterations, but effects vary by intervention type and patient-specific factors. Longitudinal, treatment-naïve studies are still needed to clarify whether dysbiosis precedes inflammation or arises as a consequence.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, IBD is characterized by a reproducible pattern of dysbiosis, including reduced microbial diversity, **depletion of beneficial SCFA-producing Firmicutes, enrichment of Proteobacteria, a lowered Firmicutes/Bacteroidetes ratio, and elevated fecal calprotectin** changes that mirror disease activity and severity. These microbiome alterations not only play a central role in the disease process but also offer valuable markers for monitoring and therapeutic targeting. While current treatments can partially restore microbial balance alongside controlling inflammation, complete microbiome recovery remains rare in severe or long-standing cases, highlighting the need for integrated strategies that combine immune modulation with targeted microbiota restoration to achieve durable remission and improve patient outcomes.

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